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S. No.	Paper Title	Author Name	Page No.
1	Socio-Economic Impact of COVID-19 on Indian Economy- A Study	Dr. M. Dillip Anand	1-4
2	A Study on Unemployment Youth and its Consequences (With Special Reference to Shahdol District)	Ragini Singh	5-8
3	A Study on the Disruptive Classroom Behaviour among Secondary Students of Kohima District	Narotola Imchen Dr. Khotole Khieya	9-13
4	A Focus on Abyei : Critical Geo-Politics on Conflict Essentialism	Amit Alok Ranjan Anum Khan	14-19
5	A Study on Employment in Special Economic Zones in Madhya Pradesh	Anil Jaiswal	20-25
6	Role of the E-Learning in Indian Higher Education: Trends and Issues	Dr. Sanjeev Kumar	26-31
7	Sustainable Development : A Study	Lt. (Dr.) Meenakshi Lohani	32-38
8	Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the World and the Indian Economy	Harshita Agarwal	39-49
9	Investigating impact of perceived organizational support and leader member exchange on career success of IT professionals: A Literature Review	Sheetal Sharma Dr. Vandana Singh	50-57
10	Entrepreneurship Development: Challenges and Possibilities in UT Jammu and Kashmir	Dr. Showkat Ahmad Sheikh	58-68
11	Employee Retention in Education Sector in India : with Special Reference to Bhopal Region	Ms. Monika Nigam Dr. Pooja Chaturvedi Dr. Neha Mathur	69-74
12	Feminism in the Poetry of P.B Shelley and Jayadeva: A Discourse Analysis	Upasana Udipt	75-79
13	The Enhanced Role of e-HRM in Light of COVID-19	Aranya	80-85
14	Film and Literature	Avinash Kumar	86-89
15	Role of Healthcare Administrators Jobs : Hospitals, Public Health, Private Practice	Shilpi Kochhar Dr. Sunil Kumar Deshpande	90-93
16	Financial Performance of Regional Rural Banks and Other Commercial Banks of Odisha , India: A Comparative Study	Meraj Hamid Priyank Mishra	94-101
17	Impact Of Population Growth On Water Resources In Bhopal City: A Case Study	Hafsa Bashir Dr. R.D Singh	102-108

Sustainable Development : A Study

Lt. (Dr.) Meenakshi Lohani

Assistant Professor, Geography, Km. Mayawati Govt. Girls P.G. College, Badalpur Gautam Buddha Nagar (U.P.)

Introduction :- Sustainable Development (SD) has become a ubiquitous development paradigm—the catchphrase for international aid agencies, the jargon of development planners, the theme of conferences and academic papers, as well as the slogan of development and environmental activists (Ukaga, Maser, & Reichenbach, 2011). The concept seems to have attracted the broadbased attention that other development concept lack(ed), and appears poised to remain the pervasive development paradigm for a long time (Scopelliti et al., 2018; Shepherd et al., 2016). However, notwithstanding its pervasiveness and popularity, murmurs of disenchantment about the concept are rife as people continue to ask questions about its meaning or definition and what it entails as well as implies for development theory and practice, without clear answers forthcoming (Montaldo, 2013; Shahzalal & Hassan, 2019; Tolba, 1984). SD therefore stands the risk of becoming a cliché like appropriate technology—a fashionable and rhetoric phrase—to which everyone pays homage but nobody seems to define with precision and exactitude (Mensah & Enu-Kwesi, 2018; Tolba, 1984).

In the attempt to move beyond the sustainability rhetoric and pursue a more meaningful agenda for sustainable development, a clear definition of this concept and explanation of its key dimensions are needed (Gray, 2010; Mensah & Enu-Kwesi, 2018). This need, according to Gray (2010), as cited in Giovannoni and Fabietti (2014), has been advocated by both academics and practitioners in order to promote sustainable development. While it cannot be disputed that literature on SD abounds, issues regarding the concept's definition, history, pillars, principles and the implications of these for human development, remain unclear to many people. Thus, the profusion of literature notwithstanding, further clarification of the unclear issues about SD is imperative since decision-makers need not only

better data and information on the linkages among the principles and pillars of SD, but also enhanced understanding of such linkages and their implication for action in the interest of human development (Abubakar, 2017; Hylton, 2019). Succinctly put, a concise and coherent discourse on SD is needed to further illuminate the pathway and trajectory to sustainable development in order to encourage citizenship rather than spectatorship. The purpose of this paper, therefore, is to contribute to the intelligibility and articulacy of the discourse on SD by providing more concise information on its meaning, evolution, associated key concepts, dimension, the relationships among the dimensions, the principles, and their implications for global, national and individual actions in the quest for SD. This is significant as it would provide researchers, policymakers and academics, as well as development practitioners and students more information about the paradigm for policy-making, decision-making and further reseason.

Definition of Sustainable Development :- The act or process of developing; growth; progress. Sustainable development: development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs .The term sustainable development began to gain wide acceptance in the late 1980s, after its appearance in Our Common Future, also known as The Brundtland Report. The result of a UN-convened commission created to propose "a global agenda for change" in the concept and practices of development, the Brundtland report signalled the urgency of re-thinking our ways of living and governing. To "responsibly meet humanity's goals and aspirations" would require new ways of considering old problems as well as international co-operation and coordination. The World Commission on Environment and Development, as

it was formally called, sought to draw the world's attention to "the accelerating deterioration of the human environment and natural resources and the consequences of that deterioration for economic and social development." In establishing the commission, the UN General Assembly explicitly called attention to two important ideas: The well-being of the environment, of economies and of people is inextricably linked. Sustainable development involves co-operation on a global scale. Sustainable development is about integration: developing in a way that benefits the widest possible range of sectors, across borders and even between generations. In other words, our decisions should take into consideration potential impact on society, the environment and the economy, while keeping in mind that: our actions will have impacts elsewhere and our actions will have an impact on the future. We tend to arrange things compartmentally, by divisions and departments, governments and communities; even households are rarely set up as holistic systems. Ministries of agriculture, finance, the interior and foreign affairs handle the issues that come under their domain. We divide up the tasks of our daily lives: work, rest, errands and holidays. It is not that we can't see business, government or home life as a "whole" – making a household budget or a corporate strategy are examples of just this type of exercise – but in the bustle of our complex lives it can be difficult to take the time to see beyond the most immediate or obvious concerns. Often, as the old saying goes, we can't see the forest for the trees. The concept of sustainable development has been used to articulate several essential shifts of perspective in how we relate to the world around us and, consequently, how we expect governments to make policies that support that world view. The term sustainable development began to gain wide acceptance in the late 1980s, after its appearance in Our Common Future, also known as The Brundtland Report. The result of a UN-convened commission created to propose "a global agenda for change" in the concept and practices of development, the Brundtland report signalled the urgency of re-thinking our ways of living and

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"Governments face the complex challenge of finding the right balance between the competing demands on natural and social resources, without sacrificing economic progress."

Environment and Sustainable Development :- Economic development and how it can improve the quality of life of people. Goods and services are produced to satisfy human wants. The production of various goods and services requires resources- both man-made and natural. As more goods are produced, more resources are used up. The process of production not only uses up resources, but also causes other problems. For example, when goods are produced in factories, the factories emit smoke which pollutes the air we breathe. Similarly, sewage discharged into rivers pollutes our drinking water. As the demand for goods and services keeps increasing, so does the demand for resources. As a result, resources are getting depleted and also being damaged irreparably. As we cut down forests, pollute the air and rivers, and mine minerals from the earth, we destroy nature. Such a destruction of nature is adversely affecting human life.

How Can We Achieve Sustainable Development?
:- we have learnt about how the growth of population and mankind's quest for economic development and a better quality of life in the last two centuries has caused a lot of problems to our environment and the planet earth. The problems we focused on were pollution, degradation and depletion of resources. We also learnt about the meaning of sustainable development and how important it is to keep in mind the development and wellbeing of future generations. But how do we achieve sustainable development? The environmental crisis we face is serious and pressing. However, by taking swift and decisive action, we can tide over the crisis. All definitions of sustainable development require that we see the world as a whole. You have already understood that the concept of sustainable development is a long-term concept that gives equal importance to development of future generations also. Sustainable development also emphasizes that

actions and measures taken in one part of the world has consequences for people in other parts of the world. For development to be sustainable we must think of development not only for our community or village or country but for the world as a whole. To give an example, if factories emit smoke in North America, then that air pollution from North America affects air quality in Asia. Similarly, pesticides sprayed in Bangladesh could harm fish stocks off the coast of West Bengal. Measures for sustainable development therefore focus on policies that must be adopted in the whole world. Some of these policies are implemented at the level of governments of individual countries while others require coordination at the international level.

Some examples of ways in which we can contribute to sustainable development are given below. Resources- finding substitutes for nonrenewable resources and using renewable resources judiciously. Solar energy, wind energy, hydropower, tidal energy and biofuels (like gobar gas) are being widely and increasingly used as substitutes for energy sources like coal, oil and natural gas that are being depleted rapidly. In many villages of India, solar energy appliances like solar cookers, solar lanterns and solar heaters are being encouraged and promoted by the government. In coastal areas the wind energy harnessed by windmills is being used to generate electricity. Recycling - to use again, to re-process. To make paper we need wood pulp which comes from trees. Therefore by recycling used paper we can contribute to saving trees from being cut down. Water is a scarce resource yet we do not use water judiciously. We can reuse rainwater by rainwater harvesting. Reduce - to use less or economize. Our consumption should be restrained to meeting our basic needs.

Food and agriculture: sustainability for the 21st century :- On our current trajectory, severe disruptions to national and regional food systems are highly likely to happen - the main question is when. Exposing unforeseen areas of consensus - with contributions from more than 70 global agri-food leaders in the business, policy, green, and

social arenas - the report lays out concrete steps for sustainable and resilient food and agriculture systems. By opening the silos of partisan thinking to invite reasoned discussion, it also exposes areas of disagreement and advances a key set of specific "high impact" areas where smart decisions will make the most difference.

Assessment of implementation of Agenda 21 and the Rio Principles :- This component of the project aimed to provide a quick but systematic assessment of the implementation of the 27 Rio Principles, as well as of progress and gaps in the implementation of 39 Chapters of Agenda 21.

Challenges and ways forward in the urban sector :- This study highlights some of the top challenges and priorities for the next 30-50 years in the urban sector and illustrates the increasing role of cities for achieving sustainability. The study takes stock of developments in the urban agenda since 1992 and outlines some of cities' new responsibilities linked with rapid urbanization and metropolitanization. It makes a case for integrated action to solve urban sustainability challenges, including governance and inclusion, and explores the vertical relationships between cities and higher levels of government and their implications for sustainability.

Building a Sustainable and Desirable Economy-in-Society-in-Nature :- This research is a synthesis of ideas about what a new economy-in-society-in-nature might look and how we might get there. The report argues that now is the right time for the transition to a new economic paradigm. It lays out a vision, objectives and concrete policies that could underpin a new model of the economy based on the worldview and principles of "ecological economics," including sustainable scale, equitable distribution and efficient allocation - a model where GDP growth is not the ultimate goal. The report makes a case for a greatly expanded commons sector of the economy and new common asset institutions to adequately deal with natural and social capital assets.

Sustainable energy systems :- Polarized and politicized views dominate the energy debate, at national, regional and global levels. This study documents the main views exist today, and suggests common 'no regret' directions for taking the debate forward to achieve sustainability in the energy sector - understood as enabling universal access to modern energy, ensuring that energy systems are managed in a sustainable way, and managing the broader interactions of the energy system with other sub-systems of modern societies.

Lessons learned from scenarios for sustainable development :- This research is a collaborative effort of 49 global modelers and scenario analysts. It draws lessons from 40 years of global sustainable development scenarios based on 98 models, with a particular focus on the most recent scenarios, many of which have been created specifically for Rio+20. Scenarios are documented in terms of ultimate goals, visions, strategy, including goals and targets, pathway characteristics, and policies and actions, as well as investment needs. Past trends towards sustainable development are compared with baseline scenarios for the future which are contrasted against sustainable development scenarios. Various synergies and trade-offs are discussed for a range of clusters of sustainable development goals. The study makes a case for renewed efforts to create global sustainable development scenarios that can resolve the most important trade-offs. It also critically reviews scenario-analysis at the science-policy interface, and makes suggestions for institutional change in this regard.

Sustainable land management for the 21st century :- This study examines the choices confronting us in terms of managing competing claims to land use in the 21st century. It synthesizes our knowledge of the processes by which land use changes occur today, in link with international and national drivers, national policies, and local contexts. It examines the strengths and shortcomings of current land use management systems and trends of land use change in countries at different levels of

development and their implications for the prospects for international instruments based on land use change control. The report also suggests possible options to improve the sustainability of land management for the next decades.

Environment and Sustainable Development :- Economic development and how it can improve the quality of life of people. Goods and services are produced to satisfy human wants. The production of various goods and services requires resources- both man-made and natural. As more goods are produced, more resources are used up. The process of production not only uses up resources, but also causes other problems. For example, when goods are produced in factories, the factories emit smoke which pollutes the air we breathe. Similarly, sewage discharged into rivers pollutes our drinking water. As the demand for goods and services keeps increasing, so does the demand for resources. As a result, resources are getting depleted and also being damaged irreparably. As we cut down forests, pollute the air and rivers, and mine minerals from the earth, we destroy nature. Such a destruction of nature is adversely affecting human life.

The concept of environmental sustainability is about the natural environment and how it remains productive and resilient to support human life. Environmental sustainability relates to ecosystem integrity and carrying capacity of natural environment (Brodhag & Taliere, 2006). It requires that natural capital be sustainably used as a source of economic inputs and as a sink for waste (Goodland & Daly, 1996). The implication is that natural resources must be harvested no faster than they can be regenerated while waste must be emitted no faster than they can be assimilated by the environment (Diesendorf, 2000; Evers, 2018). This is because the earth systems have limits or boundaries within which equilibrium is maintained.

Climate change has already shown signs of affecting biodiversity. In particular, Kumar et al. (2014) have observed that higher temperatures tend to affect the timing of reproduction in animal and plant species, migration patterns of animals

and species distributions and population sizes. Ukaga et al. (2011) have argued that while dire predictions abound, the full impacts of global warming are not known. What is clearly advisable, according to Campagnolo et al. (2018) is that, for the sake of sustainability, all societies must adjust to the emerging realities with respect to managing ecosystems and natural limits to growth.

The current rate of biodiversity loss exceeds the natural rate of extinction (UNSD, 2018c). The boundaries of the world's biomes are expected to change with climate change as species are expected to shift to higher latitudes and altitudes and as global vegetation cover changes (Peters & Lovejoy (1992) cited in Kappelle, Van Vuuren & Baas (1999). If species are not able to adjust to unfamiliar geographical distributions, their chances of survival will be reduced. It is predicted that, by the year 2080, about 20% of coastal wetlands could be lost due to sea-level rise (UNSD, 2018c). All of these are important issues of environmental sustainability because as already pointed out, they have implications for how the natural environment remains productively stable and resilient to support human life and development.

Conclusion :- SD has attracted much attention in the academic, governance, planning and development intervention space. A wide range of governmental and non-governmental entities appear to have embraced it as an appropriate development paradigm. This is because most, if not all proponents and advocates of the paradigm, virtually seem to concur that the challenges confronting humankind today such as climate change, depletion of ozone layer, water scarcity, loss of vegetation, inequality, insecurity, hunger, deprivation and poverty can be addressed by adhering to the tenets and principles of SD.

Sustainable development requires the generation and application of creative ideas and innovative design and techniques. For this reason, the UN should partner with governments, private sector, development agencies and civil society organisations (CSOs) to provide strong institutional and financial support for universities and other

research institutions for research into education, agriculture, physical development planning and land use, information and communication technology and health systems. All these should be backed by appropriate legal frameworks and strict enforcement of regulations to ensure that all the stakeholder comply with the SD agenda.

Suggestions :-

- Governments of all countries should promote "smart growth" through proper land use and alignment of their economies with nature's regeneration capacity. All countries should adopt appropriate production and consumption practices that fully align with the planet's ecological processes. This could be done through taxation and subsidy policies which accentuate the acceptable and eliminate unacceptable outcomes. In this respect, all countries should, for example, regarding pollution, enforce the polluter-pays-principle whereby governments require environment-polluting entities to bear the costs of their pollution rather than impose those costs on others or on the environment.
- Population growth should be checked through population policies backed by legal frameworks. Unless special action is taken, population growth coupled with increased resource consumption beyond what the earth can accommodate, will lead to the decline in or the collapse of the environment, economy and society. All countries need to have population policies that seek to check unbridled population growth. In this connection, the UN should have a global policy on population growth and ensure that member countries comply with the policy.
- There is the need for all countries to formulate and implement social policies that foster tolerance, social cohesion and justice as cornerstones of social interactions. This can be done by enshrining universal human rights within a framework of citizenship,

inclusion, equity and effective political governance.

- There should be constant education on SD by the UN and the governments of all countries as well as civil society organization to all people resident everywhere. The sensitization programmes should be directed at ensuring that every country's residents understand the concept and principles of sustainable development and engage in responsible environmental, economic and social behavior as well as accountable stewardship.
- Sustainable development requires the generation and application of creative ideas and innovative design and techniques. For this reason, the UN should partner with governments, private sector, development agencies and civil society organizations (CSOs) to provide strong institutional and financial support for universities and other research institutions for research into education, agriculture, physical development planning and land use, information and communication technology and health systems. All these should be backed by appropriate legal frameworks and strict enforcement of regulations to ensure that all the stakeholder comply with the SD agenda.
- In prosecuting the SD agenda, UN should acknowledge and consider different national capacities and levels of development and respect national policies and priorities. The UN should also ensure that all countries emphasize universality with country-specific approach to the global goals, and encourage the developed countries to support the developing ones in the implementation of the global agenda.

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